

Supplementary Material

Phylogenetic Systematics of the shieldtail snake genus *Teretrurus* Beddome, 1886 (Squamata, Uropeltidae) reveals extensive cryptic diversity and novel geographic spread in the Western Ghats of India

Vivek Philip Cyriac^{1*}, Ganesh S.R.², Zeba Madani³ Avrajjal Ghosh⁴, Vidisha Kulkarni¹, Kartik Shanker¹

¹ Centre for Ecological Sciences, Indian Institute of Science, CV Raman Rd, Bengaluru, Karnataka – 560012, India.

² Kalinga Centre for Rainforest Ecology, Kalinga Mane, Churrchihakklu, Agumbe Hobli, Hosur Grama, Guddekere, Shivamogga, Karnataka – 577411, India.

³ Department of Biodiversity, Wildlife Conservation and Management, Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan, Bhavans College, Mumbai, India.

⁴ School of Biological Sciences, National Institute of Science Education and Research (NISER), Bhubaneswar, Odisha – 752050, India.

*** Corresponding author:** Vivek Philip Cyriac, Centre for Ecological Sciences, Indian Institute of Science, CV Raman Rd, Bengaluru, Karnataka – 560012, India.

Email: vivek.cyriac@gmail.com, Ph: +917593978351

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0465-0452

Running title: Cryptic diversity in the fossorial snake genus *Teretrurus*

Table S1: Morphometric measurements of 37 *Teretrurus* specimens examined during this study

Species	<i>T. hewstoni</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>					
ID NO	VPTS1015055	VPTS1015056	VPTS0918094	VPTS0918095	VPTH0721122	VPTH0721123	VPBR0514019	VPBR1014021	VPTS0920118
Locality	Wayanad	Wayanad	Wayanad	Wayanad	Wayanad	Wayanad	Marayoor	Marayoor	Marayoor
SuL	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4
InL	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3
DS	14:15:15	14:15:15	15:15:15	13:15:15	13:15:15	13:15:15	15:15:15	13:15:15	13:15:15
VS	125	122	118	122	126	123	143	148	149
SC	7	8	6	5	6	7	7	9	7
SVL	141.9	136.8	128.1	146.2	122.6	127.7	222.9	198.8	174.8
TL	6.1	5.2	4.9	4.8	4.4	6.3	7.1	8.2	6.2
AW	3.5	3.2	3.8	4.4	4.3	4.4	7	5.4	4.4
MW	4.3	4	4.4	4.6	4.2	4.4	9.9	7.1	5.2
VW	3.5	3.4	3.4	3.6	2.5	3.9	6.3	4.8	4.6
HL	5.3	5.1	4.9	5.4	4.5	5.4	6.9	6.4	6.4
HW	2.9	2.7	3.3	3.8	3	3.1	4.4	4.6	3.9
RL	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.7	0/6	0.5
ED	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.9	0.7	0.7	1.1	1	1
OL	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.3	1.5	1.7	1.6	1.6
IOD	1.9	1.8	2	2	2	2	2.7	2.7	2.3
IND	0.8	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	1.2	1	1
SL	2.1	2.2	2.2	2.3	2.1	2.3	3.1	2.8	2.7
FL	2.3	2.2	2.1	2.6	1.9	2.3	3	2.8	2.8
FW	1	0.9	1.2	1.3	1.1	1.3	1.9	1.8	1.9
PL	2	1.9	1.7	2	1.7	2	2.8	2.6	2.4
PW	0.9	1	1	1.2	1	1	1.7	1.5	1.6
IPS	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.9	0.7	0.8
PFL	1.4	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.3	1.5	2.3	2.1	2.1
PFW	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.8	1.4	1.5
IPFS	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.8	1	1.3	1.1	1.2
NL	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.1	0.9	1	1	1.1	1.2
NW	0.8	0.9	1	1.1	0.9	1	1.3	1.2	1.1
INS	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.4

Table S1 continued..

Species	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	<i>T. sanguineus</i>	<i>T. travancoricus</i>	<i>T. travancoricus</i>	<i>T. travancoricus</i>	<i>T. travancoricus</i>
ID NO	ZSI/WGRC/25 26a	ZSI/WGRC/25 26b	ZSI/WGRC/25 26c	ZSI/WGRC/25 26d	VPTS0315032	VPTS0515035	VPTS1215077	ZSI/WGRC/2613
Locality	Marayoor	Marayoor	Marayoor	Marayoor	KMTR	Pandimotta	Pandimotta	Pandimotta
SuL	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4
InL	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3
DS	15:15:14	15:15:15	13:15:15	15:15:15	15:15:15	13:15:15	15:15:15	15:15:15
VS	148	150	149	148	130	139	142	139
SC	10	7	10	10	8	7	6	9
SVL	188.4	198.2	158.9	162.1	139.4	135.9	209.4	111.7
TL	6.6	4.8	6.1	6.9	7.6	5.1	5.6	5.3
AW	5.2	6.1	5.1	4.4	4.7	4.9	5	3.1
MW	6.2	7.6	5.1	6	5.5	5.6	6.9	4.3
VW	3.9	5.4	3.9	4	3.6	3.7	4.1	2.6
HL	6.8	7.4	6.1	6.3	6.4	5.6	7.3	4.8
HW	4.6	5.2	4.1	4.1	3.8	3.1	4.2	3.1
RL	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.5
ED	1	1	0.9	0.9	1.1	0.9	1	0.8
OL	1.7	1.8	1.6	1.6	1.7	1.5	1.8	1.3
IOD	2.6	3.2	2.6	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.4	1.7
IND	1.1	1.4	1.1	1.1	1.3	1	1.4	0.8
SL	3	3.3	2.8	2.7	2.5	2.5	2.9	2.1
FL	2.9	3.1	2.7	2.8	2.6	2.3	3	2
FW	1.7	2	1.8	1.7	1.4	1.3	1.6	1.2
PL	2.7	2.7	2.3	2.4	2.3	2.1	3	1.8
PW	1.5	1.7	1.4	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.6	1.1
IPS	0.7	0.8	0.6	0.7	0.9	0.6	1.2	0.6
PFL	2.1	2.4	2.1	2.1	1.3	1.3	1.5	0.9
PFW	1.7	1.7	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.2	1.8	1.3
IPFS	1.2	1.4	1.2	1.3	0.9	0.6	1	0.6
NL	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.1	1.3	1.1	1.5	0.9
NW	1.3	1.5	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.5	1
INS	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.6	0.2

Table S1 continued..

Species	<i>T. travancoricus</i>	<i>T. rhodogaster</i>						
ID NO	CESS320	BNHS S107	BNHS S108	BNHS S109	BNHS S110	BNHS S111	BNHS S112a	BNHS S112b
Locality	Unspecified							
SuL	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4
InL	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3
DS	15:15:15	14:15:15	15:15:15	15:15:15	13:15:15	13:15:15	15:15:15	13:15:15
VS	134	141	149	144	140	138	143	142
SC	7	11	7	7/8 (R/L)	10	7	7	10
SVL	174.2	173.4	193.3	190.6	116.4	112.1	167.8	155.1
TL	6.8	9.6	6.7	5.4	5.6	3.9	5.2	6.9
AW	5.1	4.6	5	4.9	3.6	3.3	3.9	3.7
MW	6	5.8	6.3	5.5	4.4	3.7	5.7	4.8
VW	3.2	4	4.2	3.8	3.6	2.2	3.7	3.4
HL	5.8	6	-	6.1	4.6	4.7	5.5	5.4
HW	3.9	3.6	-	3.7	2.8	2.9	3.4	3.1
RL	0.4	0.5	-	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5
ED	1	0.9	-	0.9	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.7
OL	1.5	1.6	-	1.5	1.3	1.2	1.4	1.4
IOD	2.4	2.4	-	2.4	1.9	1.9	2.2	2.1
IND	1.1	1	-	1	0.8	0.7	0.9	0.8
SL	2.5	2.6	-	2.5	2.1	2.1	2.3	2.3
FL	2.6	2.8	-	2.6	2.2	2.2	2.6	2.4
FW	1.3	1.9	-	1.8	1.5	1.5	1.8	1.7
PL	2	2.6	-	2.4	2	1.9	2.1	2.1
PW	0.9	1.4	-	1.4	1.3	1.1	1.2	1.3
IPS	0.9	0.4	-	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3
PFL	1.3	2.1	-	2.3	1.6	1.6	1.8	1.7
PFW	1.5	1.4	-	1.5	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.2
IPFS	0.7	1.3	-	1.4	1	1	1.1	1
NL	1.3	1.1	-	1	1	0.9	1	1
NW	1.3	1.2	-	1.1	1	0.9	1	1
INS	0.5	0.5	-	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4

Table S1 continued..

Species	<i>T. albiventer</i> sp. nov.							
ID NO	ZSI/WGRC/194 07	BNHS 3757	BNHS 3756	VPTS0522152	VPTS0522153	CESS077	CESS118	CESS120
Locality	Peppara							
SuL	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4
InL	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3
DS	15:15:14	12:15:15	12:15:15	13:16:15	12:15:15	15:15:15	14:15:15	15:15:15
VS	134	130	139	135	134	131	139	135
SC	6	10	10	6	9	7	6	9
SVL	173.66	153.6	160.9	111.3	126.1	187.4	181.9	152.8
TL	6.34	8.4	8.1	3.7	6.9	6.6	6.1	8.2
AW	4.8	4.8	5	4	3.9	5.3	4.7	4.4
MW	6.8	5.7	6	4.6	4.9	5.6	5.1	4.6
VW	3.9	3.3	3.9	2.7	3.8	4	3.4	2.8
HL	6.2	6.4	6.2	5.2	5.5	6.9	6.1	6.6
HW	4.2	4.4	4.3	3.5	4.2	4.6	3.8	3.7
RL	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.6
ED	0.9	1	1.1	0.9	0.9	1.2	1	1
OL	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.5	1.5	1.8	1.5	1.6
IOD	2.4	2.4	2.6	2	2.3	2.8	2.4	2.4
IND	1.2	1.2	1.1	0.9	1.2	1.1	1	1
SL	2.7	2.6	2.6	2.2	2.5	3	2.5	2.6
FL	2.7	2.5	2.7	2.3	2.4	2.9	2.7	2.6
FW	1.6	1.7	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.7	1.7	1.7
PL	2.6	2.8	2.6	2.1	2.5	2.6	2.6	2.5
PW	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.7
IPS	1	1.3	1.1	0.9	1	0.9	0.9	1
PFL	1.2	1.5	1.3	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.2	1.3
PFW	1.6	1.4	1.7	1.4	1.5	1.7	1.6	1.5
IPFS	0.8	1	0.9	0.7	0.9	1.1	0.8	0.8
NL	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.3	1.3
NW	1.4	1	1.3	1.1	1.1	1.6	1.3	1.1
INS	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.5

Table S1 continued..

Species	<i>T. siruvaniensis</i> sp. nov.	<i>T. siruvaniensis</i> sp. nov.	<i>T. periyarensis</i> sp. nov.	<i>T. agumbensis</i> sp. nov.	<i>T. agumbensis</i> sp. nov.	<i>T. agumbensis</i> sp. nov.
ID NO	BNHS 3759	BNHS 3758	BNHS 3760	BNHS 3761	BNHS 3761	VPTS1023191
Locality	Siruvani	Siruvani	Vandiperiyar	Agumbe	Agumbe	Agumbe
SuL	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4	4/4
InL	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3	3/3
DS	13:15:15	15:15:15	13:15:15	14:15:15	14:15:15	14:15:15
VS	129	127	152	127	122	116
SC	6	8	9	7	8	7
SVL	123.8	134.5	146.7	128.3	143	121.8
TL	4.2	6.5	7.3	5.7	6	5.2
AW	4.1	4.4	4	4.3	4	3.9
MW	4.8	5.6	4.9	4.9	4.2	4.7
VW	3.1	4.3	3	4	3.9	3.3
HL	5	5.2	5.5	5.4	5.2	4.7
HW	2.9	3.3	3.4	3.1	3.1	3.1
RL	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
ED	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.9	0.7
OL	1.3	1.2	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.3
IOD	1.8	1.7	2.4	2	1.9	1.8
IND	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.8	0.9	0.8
SL	2	2.1	2.5	2.4	2.1	1.9
FL	2.1	2	2.5	2.7	2.3	2.4
FW	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.3	1.1	1.2
PL	1.9	1.9	2.1	2.3	2	1.7
PW	1	1.1	1.1	1	0.9	0.8
IPS	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.4	0.4	0.3
PFL	1.5	1.4	1.7	1.5	1.3	1.2
PFW	1.1	1	1.5	1.2	1.2	1.2
IPFS	0.8	0.9	1.2	0.9	0.9	0.7
NL	0.9	1.1	0.9	1.1	1	1
NW	0.9	0.9	1.1	1.1	1.1	1
INS	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.3

***Note:** Voucher code indicate the museum of deposition. ZSI/WGRC: Zoological Survey of India Western Ghats Regional Centre, Kozhikode, Kerala; BNHS: Bombay Natural History Society, Mumbai; CESS: Centre for Ecological Science, Bangalore. The VP series of specimens are also deposited in the museum of the Centre for Ecological Science, Bangalore.